

Muslim Higher Education System and Institutions in Uganda

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Abstract

Since the inaugural World Conference on Muslim Education in Makkah (1977), significant recommendations have been made to reform Muslim education systems, particularly through the Islamization of knowledge. As a member of the Organisation of Islamic Cooperation (OIC), Uganda was expected to adopt these reforms within its Islamic institutions of higher learning. This study evaluates the extent to which such institutions in Uganda have implemented the Islamization of knowledge and integrated it into their academic curricula. Employing a systematic seven-step review methodology, the research analyzed publicly available curricular data submitted to the Uganda National Council for Higher Education (UNCHE) and compared program offerings from recognized Islamic institutions in Uganda. Findings reveal that only three institutions—Islamic University in Uganda (IUIU), Islamic Call University College (ICUC), and Al-Mustafa Islamic College (AIC)—are formally recognized. IUIU is fully registered, while ICUC and AIC hold provisional status. Of the 104 programs offered by IUIU and 25 by AIC, none demonstrate substantial incorporation of Naql (revealed knowledge) alongside Aql (acquired knowledge). The curricula predominantly reflect secular frameworks, with limited visibility of Islamic epistemological integration as envisioned by the 1977 Makkah Conference. This study concludes that the Islamization of knowledge in Uganda’s Islamic higher education institutions remains underdeveloped. The current curriculum reform trajectory falls short of achieving the comprehensive objectives of Islamic education, underscoring the need for a more balanced integration of Qur’anic principles, rational inquiry, and empirical sciences to meet the holistic educational needs of Muslim learners.

Keywords: Muslim, Higher Education, Curriculum, Uganda

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Introduction

The Islamic educational system stands out as significant, especially emphasizing maşdar, “produced you,” and “settled you.” Surah Hud 11:61 of the Qur'an provides insight.

And to the people of Thamûd, We sent their brother Şâlih. He said, “O my people! Worship Allah. You have no god other than Him. He is the One Who’ produced you from the earth and settled you on it. So, seek His forgiveness and turn to Him in repentance. Surely my Lord is Ever Near, All-Responsive to prayers’ (Mustafa Khattab, 2025)

Education from an Islamic perspective with an Islamic worldview is essential. This paper aims to explore the real needs of education for the Muslim community to achieve prosperity and success in this world and the hereafter. The research report consists of five main sections. Apart from the abstract, the first section covers the introduction, definitions of terms, background of the study, identification of the problem, and the study's objectives. Section two discusses the research methodology, while section three presents the findings of the study. Section four offers a discussion, and the final section provides the conclusion.

This section outlines the Islamization of Knowledge, Integration of Knowledge, and Curriculum Design, which are essential components for any knowledge seeker. Islamization of knowledge is a process where secular elements are identified and separated from a body of knowledge, and Islamic principles are infused into it. (Rosnani Hashim, 2019). Integration of knowledge involves merging two or more originally unrelated knowledge structures into a single entity. Curriculum refers to the subjects that comprise a course of study in a school or college (university).

This article recognizes the importance of Watanic jurisprudence in reclaiming Islamic worldviews and principles within modern knowledge and science. Watanic jurisprudence is a methodological framework that reorients constitutional theory and legal analysis towards a Qur’anic epistemology. At its core, it offers a structured approach to re-establish knowledge and governance grounded in divine principles by examining how sovereignty informs the constitutional order. It proposes two contrasting legal-philosophical models: the continuum and the dichotomy. These models serve as epistemic tools for understanding the ontological source of law and the nature of political authority. The continuum framework affirms that law, governance, and knowledge are inseparable from their metaphysical and religious foundations. Within this model, sovereignty is a divine trust (*amanah*) that integrates spiritual values with temporal authority. A continuity between divine revelation and societal application thus animates the constitutional system. Law is conceived not merely as a regulatory system but as a moral extension of divine will, shaping a nation whose identity is rooted in indigenous ethos and transcendent guidance. This model enables the reintegration of knowledge and science with Qur’anic norms, affirming tawhidic unity between the sacred and the rational. In contrast, the dichotomous framework reflects a secular epistemology, wherein sovereignty is constructed upon human ideologies detached from divine reference. Legal authority in this model emerges from political constructs such as parliamentary supremacy, socialism, or other temporal doctrines. Religion is confined to the private sphere, while law and governance operate autonomously from metaphysical claims. (Husain, 2017, 2018, 2025)

The framework of Watanic jurisprudence signifies a paradigmatic shift from the traditional unity of knowledge towards a fragmented and anthropocentric worldview. From the perspective of Watanic jurisprudence, the central epistemological question concerns the source and legitimacy of authority: whether sovereignty is a divine mandate or a human invention.

This question has profound implications for the interpretation of the rule of law, the ethics of governance, and the classification of knowledge itself. Thus, Watanic jurisprudence offers a critical methodology for deconstructing secular paradigms and reconstructing a system of governance, knowledge, and science that aligns with the Qur'anic worldview, where truth, authority, and justice are unified under divine sovereignty. The indigenous factors also contribute to interpreting Islam within the principles ordained by Allah the Almighty. (Husain, 2021, 2025). By adapting the Watanic jurisprudence, Islamization of Knowledge, Integration of Knowledge, and curriculum design gain legitimacy in the institutional system.

Background of the Study

The first World Conference of Muslim Education took place in Makkah, Saudi Arabia, in April 1977. One of its objectives was to address the rising challenges of moral decline; consequently, the lack of a visible Islamic alternative value system in higher education faced significant obstacles in tackling these issues in both majority and minority Muslim countries (Ghulam Nabi Saqeb, 2000).

A key conclusion from this conference was to promote the establishment of an Islamic university, emphasizing the Islamization of knowledge and its integration. In 1974, the Ugandan government endorsed the construction of Islamic universities through multiple legal frameworks (Ismail S. Gyagenda and Wardah M. Rajab-Gyagenda, 2016).

Nonetheless, these institutions began operating in the late 1980s and early 1990s, a trend that continues today. The HEIM (Epistemological Integration Model)—IW (Islamic Worldview) paradigm was used to analyze the curriculum of Muslim higher education. The HEIM-IW includes sources and tools for integrating human epistemology. A brief illustration is provided below.

The main source of knowledge integration is Wahyu (revelation), or written divine revelation, including both the Qur'an and Sunnah, which are regarded as the highest authority for all human knowledge. The second source is the constructed world, which consists of four domains: firstly, the natural realm; secondly, the physical realm; thirdly, the social realm—which includes individuals, families, tribes, linguistic groups, cultures, and civilizations; and fourthly, the psychological realm, relating to the human soul in terms of mind, spirit, thought, and the behavior of the khalifah. Instruments for the integration of human epistemology.

Reason, the tertiary source of rationality, serves as the tool for integrating human epistemology. It utilizes the senses as the mechanism for combining human knowledge. As tools for understanding the aims of the revelation, they mutually support individuals' efforts to interpret and enact the message conveyed by this revelation. (Quran: Al-Játhiyah 45:5).

Written divine revelation, the created world, and reason are sources and tools of integration of human epistemology, complementing one another in enabling human beings to access greater knowledge. (Fathi Hassan Malkawi, 2019, pp. 177 - 214)

So, the aim of Islamic epistemology is deeply rooted in all sources of knowledge. However, to provide context for the literature review, emphasis is placed on the Qur'an as a source, particularly Surah Ibrahim and Isra (17).

فَاعْلَمْ أَنَّهُ لَا إِلَهَ إِلَّا اللَّهُ وَاسْتَغْفِرْ لِذَنْبِكَ وَلِلْمُؤْمِنِينَ وَالْمُؤْمِنَاتِ ۗ وَاللَّهُ يَعْلَمُ مَتَّعَلِبَكُمْ وَمَثُوكُمْ

So, know 'well, O Prophet,' that there is no god 'worthy of worship' except Allah. And seek forgiveness for your shortcomings and for 'the sins of' the believing men and women. For Allah 'fully' knows your movements and places of rest 'O people' Qur'an Suratul Ibrahim 47:19

وَلَا تَقْفُ مَا لَيْسَ لَكَ بِهِ عِلْمٌ ۗ إِنَّ السَّمْعَ وَالْبَصَرَ وَالْفُؤَادَ كُلُّ أُولَٰئِكَ كَانَ عَنْهُ مَسْئُولًا

Do not follow what you have no 'sure' knowledge of. Indeed, all will be called to account for 'their' hearing, sight, and intellect. Qur'an Suratul Isra 17(36)

This article focuses on the primary and secondary sources on the themes of Muslim education at the higher education level, and the literature review is presented below. The purpose of this study is to evaluate the influence that the curriculum at Islamic higher education institutions has on the Islamization of knowledge and the introduction of Islamic concepts into other areas of study and educational programs.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopts a qualitative descriptive analysis approach to evaluate the influence and structure of the curriculum used by Islamic institutions of higher learning in Uganda. A seven-step systematic review method was applied to analyze the curricula submitted to the Uganda National Council for Higher Education (UNCHE). This review was based on data accessible via the UNCHE's official online database, complemented by comparative analysis with curricula published online by certified Islamic higher education institutions operating within Uganda.

Data Sources and Classification

To ensure a rigorous evaluation, the study surveyed ten (10) key sources of literature, categorized into primary and secondary data. Primary Data on ME and Higher Education: Out of the ten (10) surveyed types of literature sources, primary data. They are highlighted according to their titles, the focus of their study, the author(s), the years of publication, and their methods, which are highlighted below:

First, Islamic University In Uganda (IUIU): The Pioneers (Article): Source Primary Focus of the Study: Establishment of Islamic University in Uganda. Authors: Ismail S. Gyagenda and Wardah M. Rajab-Gyagenda. Year of Publication: 2016. Methods: Interviews.(Ismail S. Gyagenda and Wardah M. Rajab-Gyagenda, 2016)

Second, Conflict Management in Higher Education Institutions (HEIs): A Case Study of Islamic University in Uganda (Article): Source: Primary Focus of the Study: Management Conflicts at the Islamic University in Uganda. Author: Farooq Mirro Year of Publication: 2022 Method: interview. (Farooq Miuro, 2022).

Secondary Data on ME and Higher Education: Secondary data accounts for eight out of the ten types of literature sources surveyed. Highlighted below, according to their titles, the focus of their study, the author(s), the years of publication, and their methods:

First, *Some Reflections on Islamization of Education Since the 1977 Makkah Conference: Accomplishments, Failures, and Tasks Ahead*. Source: Secondary. Focus of the study: Review the Islamization of Knowledge progress in the post-First World Muslim Education Conference. Author: Ghulam Nabi Saqeb. Year of Publication: 2000. Method: Library Research

Second, *the problem of Muslim education in Uganda: some reflections (Article)* Study: Source: secondary Focus of the Study: Muslim Concerns with Colonial Education: Arthur Abasi Kiyimba. Year of Publication: 2007. Methods – Qualitative – Library Research (Abasi Kiyimba, 2007)

Three, *what makes a good minority Muslim? Educational policy and the paradoxes of Muslim schooling in Uganda*. Source: Secondary. The focus of the study: Education as a field of moral debate: Arthur Dorothea Schulz. Year of publication: 2013. Methods – Qualitative – Library Research and limited interview. (Dorothea E. Schulz, 2013)

Four: *Islamic Education in Uganda: Challenges and Prospects of Islamization of Knowledge*. Type of Literature Source: Secondary data (Article): Focus of the Study: performance of the prevailing Islamic education in Uganda and how Islamisation of human-acquired knowledge can figure into improvement of the performance of this curriculum to foster modernity. (Authors: Sulaiman Lujja, Mustafa Omar Muhammed, and Rusni Hassan; Year of Publication: 2016) Methods: qualitative—library research (i.e., information was collected using library searches, where books, journal articles, periodicals, and online resources were used in gathering data.) (Sulaiman Lujja, Mustafa Omar Muhammed and Rusni Hassan, 2016)

Five, *Rethinking Reforms in Higher Education from Islamization to Integration of Knowledge (Book)*: Source: Second. Focus of the study: Reforms in Higher Education from Islamization to Integration of Knowledge and Language. Authors: Ziauddin Sardar and Jeremy Henzell Thomas. Year of Publication: (2017): Methods: Library research. (Ziauddin Sardar and Jeremy Henzell - Thomas, 2017)

Six: *Contribution of the Madrasah System to the Development of Human Resources in Uganda and Its Neighboring Countries*: Source: Secondary; Focus of the Study: The Madrassah and its development of human resources in Uganda. (Article) Author: Sulait D. Kabali, Year of Publication: 2019 Method: Qualitative – Library Research (Sulaiti Dawud Kabali, 2019)

Seven, *The Relevance of Al-Ghazali's Educational Views to the Contemporary System of Muslim Education: Focus on Islamic Education in Uganda (Article)* Source: Secondary, Focus of the Study: Al-Ghazali's Educational Views on the Contemporary System of Muslim Education: Islamic Education: Author: AbdulSwamad Gyagenda. Year of Publication: 2021 Method: Qualitative – Library Research. (AbdulSwamad Gyagenda, 2021)

Eight, *University of the Future Leading the Way (Book)*. Source: Secondary: Focus of the Study: Practices of Reinventing Future University: A Case Study of International Islamic University Malaysia. Author, Abdul Rashid Moten. Year of Publication: 2023. Method: Library Research. (Abdul Rashid Moten, 2023)

Research Gap

Upon reviewing the literature above, considering their thematic focus, authorship, year of publication, and methodological approaches, it is clear that no existing study has directly analyzed the curriculum of Islamic institutions of higher learning in Uganda in relation to national regulatory mechanisms such as those set by UNCHE. This notable gap in scholarly discourse highlights the importance and need for the present study, which aims to address this gap by providing a systematic, descriptive analysis of the curricular frameworks and regulatory intersections impacting Islamic higher education in Uganda.

Data From the Regulator

This section presents the results of the Islamic Institutions of Higher Education accreditation and curriculum status in Uganda. (Uganda National Council for Higher Education, 2025)

Islamic Institution of Higher Education Accreditation Status

First, Islamic universities in Uganda, namely, Islamic University in Uganda (IUIU), Islamic Call University College (ICUC), and Al-Mustafah Islamic College (AIC), are the only ones accredited to teach at the higher education level. Secondly, the institutional type of Islamic university in Uganda, Islamic Call University, and Al-Mustafa Islamic College is private. Three, the award type: IUIU University—Registered, ICUC, Provisional License to operate as another degree-awarding institution, AIC, Provisional License to operate as a university. The fourth Islamic University In Uganda (IUIU) has four campuses to operate in Arua, Mbale, and two in Kampala. ICUC has one campus in Kampala, and AIC has one campus in Kampala. For more details refer to table 1 below on the Islamic Institution of Higher Education accreditation status.

S/N	Name	Institution type	Award type	District
1.	IUIU	Private	University –	Mbale Kampala (2) Arua
2.	ICUC	Private	Provisional License to Operate as Other Degree Awarding Institution	Kampala
3.	AIC	Private	Provisional License to Operate as University	Kampala

Source: The regulator as per June and July 2025

Curriculum

Throughout the remaining parts of this study, the phrase “the regulator “or the abbreviation UNCHE refers to the Uganda National Council of Higher Education. For Islamic institutions of higher learning, Islamic University in Uganda is also referred to in this study as U1, Islamic Call University College as U2, and Al-Mustafa Islamic College as U3.

Postgraduate - Doctor of Philosophy

According to the Uganda National Council of Higher Education (UNCHE), several Doctor of Philosophy curricula are accredited by the regulator for U1. It approved the following nine (9) PhD programs to run at U1: history, education, Sharia, Arabic, Islamic studies, Islamic banking and finance, business administration, Kiswahili, and law.

U1’s nine (9) Doctor of Philosophy programs include ‘History and Education Curricula,’ which was launched on 27th August 2018 and will expire on 27th August 2028. The Arabic and Islamic Studies curriculum was launched on 30th November 2018 and will expire on 30th November 2028. The Islamic Banking and Finance curriculum was launched on 1st March 2022 and will expire on 1st March 2031. The business administration curriculum was launched on 14th March 2022 and will expire on 14th March 2032. The Kiswahili curriculum was launched on 22nd January 2024 and will expire on 22nd January 2024, and the law curriculum was launched on 28th April 2025 and will expire on 28th April 2035.

For more detail as regards Doctor of Philosophy curricula at U1, see table 2 below.

S/N	Name	Accredited Date	Expiry Date	Status
1.	PhD in History	27/Aug/2018	27/Aug/2028	Active
2.	PhD in Education	27/Aug/2018	27/Aug/2028	Active
3.	PhD in Sharia	30/Nov/2018	30/Nov/2028	Active
4.	PhD in Arabic	30/Nov/2018	30/Nov/2028	Active
5.	PhD in Islamic Studies	30/Nov/2018	30/Nov/2028	Active
6.	PhD in Islamic Banking and Finance	01/Mar/2021	01/Mar/2031	Active
7.	PhD in Business Administration	14/Mar/2022	14/Mar/2032	Active
8.	PhD in Kiswahili	22/Jan/2024	22/Jan/2034	Active
9.	PhD in Law	28/April/2025	28/April/2035	Active

Source: The Regulator as of June and July 2025

However, for U2 and U3, there is no accreditation or activation of the curriculum available for the Doctor of Philosophy.

Postgraduate - Masters

The Regulator licensed a total of nineteen (19) master curricula to U1. The programs, along with their activation and expiry dates, are highlighted as follows:

Starting with Education (M.Ed. Specialization), activated on 1st March 2021 and expiring on 1st March 2026. Educational Psychology, activated on 1st March 2021, expires on 1st March 2026. The law was activated on 13th December 2021 and expires on 1st March 2026. International Relations was activated on 20th January 2023 and expires on 20th January 2028. History was activated on 20th January 2023 and expires on 20th January 2028. Business Administration was activated on 17th April 2023 and expires on 20th January 2028. Public Administration was activated on 17th April 2023 and expires on 20th January 2028. Religion, Peace, and Conflict Resolution, activated on 21st August 2023, expires on 21st August 2028. Sharia was activated on 21st August 2023 and expires on 21st August 2028. The Arabic language was activated on 21st August 2023 and expires on 21st August 2028. Islamic Banking and Finance was activated on 13th October 2023 and expires on 13th October 2028. Communications and Media Studies was activated on 22nd January 2024 and expires on 29th January 2029. Islamic Studies (English) was activated on 22nd January 2024 and expires on 29th January 2029. Kiswahili was activated on 22nd January 2024 and expires on 29th January 2029. Environmental Science was activated on 22nd January 2024 and expires on 29th January 2029. Botany and Zoology were activated on 22nd January 2024 and expires on 29th January 2029. Islamic Studies (Arabic version) was activated on 22nd January 2024 and expires on 29th January 2029. Economics was activated on 30th January 2025 and expires on 30th January 2030; and ending with a master's in social work, activated on 30th January 2025, expires on 30th January 2030. For more details regarding master's curricula at U3, see table 3 below.

Table 3 U1 Postgraduate – Master's Program

S/N	Name	Accredited date	Expiry Date	Status
1.	Education (M.Ed. with Specialisations)	01/Mar/2021	01/Mar/2026	Active
2.	Educational Psychology	01/Mar/2021	01/Mar/2026	Active
3.	Laws	13/Dec/2021	13/Dec/2026	Active
4.	International Relations	20/Jan/2023	20/Jan/2028	Active
5.	History	20/Jan/2023	20/Jan/2028	Active
6.	Business Administration	17/Apr/2023	17/Apr/2028	Active
7.	Public Administration and Management	17/Apr/2023	17/Apr/2028	Active
8.	Religion, Peace, and Conflict Resolution	21/Aug/2023	21/Aug/2028	Active
9.	Sharia	21/Aug/2023	21/Aug/2028	Active
10.	Arabic Language	21/Aug/2023	21/Aug/2028	Active
11.	Islamic Banking and Finance	13/Oct/2023	13/Oct/2028	Active
12.	Communication and Media Studies	22/Jan/2024	22/Jan/2029	Active
13.	Islamic Studies – English	22/Jan/2024	22/Jan/2029	Active
14.	Kiswahili	22/Jan/2024	22/Jan/2029	Active
15.	Environmental Science	22/Jan/2024	22/Jan/2029	Active
16.	Botany and Zoology	22/Jan/2024	22/Jan/2029	Active
17.	Islamic Studies (Arabic Version)	22/Jan/2024	22/Jan/2029	Active
18.	Economics	30/Jan/2025	30/Jan/2030	Active
19.	Social Work	30/Jan/2025	30/Jan/2030	Active

Source: The Regulator as per June and July 2025

However, for U2 and U3, as previously seen with the Doctor of Philosophy, there is neither accreditation nor activation of the curriculum of Master's curricula found in the regulators' online database.

Postgraduate Diploma

The regulator approved ten (10) curricula for the post-diploma program at UI. The diploma curricula activated by the regulator, along with their expiry dates, are highlighted as follows: Postgraduate Diploma in Project Planning and Management, activated 17th April 2023, expires 17th April 2028. Postgraduate Diploma in Human Resources Management, activated 17th April 2023, expires 17th April 2028. Postgraduate Diploma in Management and Teaching Higher Education, activated 21st August 2023, expires 21st August 2028. Postgraduate Diploma in Islamic Banking and Finance, activated 13th October 2023, expires 13th October 2028. The Postgraduate Diploma in Educational Management and Administration, activated on 22nd January 2024, expires on 22nd January 2029. The Postgraduate Diploma in International Affairs and Humanitarian Diplomacy, activated on 10th July 2024, expires in 2029. The Postgraduate Diploma in Education and Child Protection and Welfare, activated on 22nd January 2024, expires on 22nd January 2029.

For more details regarding postgraduate diploma curricula at U1, see table 4 below

S/N	Name	Accredited Date	Expiration Date	Status
1.	Postgraduate Diploma in Project Planning and Management	17/Apr/2023	17/Apr/2028	Active
2.	Postgraduate Diploma in Human Resource Management	17/Apr/2023	17/Apr/2028	Active
3.	Postgraduate Diploma in Public Administration and Management	17/Apr/2023	17/Apr/2028	Active
4.	Postgraduate Diploma in Management and Teaching Higher Education	21/Aug/2023	21/Aug/2028	Active
5.	Postgraduate Diploma in Islamic Banking and Finance	13/Oct/2023	13/Oct/2028	Active
6.	Postgraduate Diploma in Education, Management and Administration	22/Jan/2024	22/Jan/2029	Active
7.	Postgraduate Diploma in International Affairs and Humanitarian Diplomacy	10/Jul/2024	10/Jul/2029	Active
8.	Postgraduate Diploma in Education	10/Jul/2024	10/Jul/2029	Active
9.	Postgraduate Diploma in Child Protection and Welfare	30/Jan/2025	30/Jan/2030	Active
10.	Postgraduate Diploma in International Relations and Diplomacy	30/Jan/2025	30/Jan/2030	Active

Source: The Regulator as per June and July 2025

The regulator approved five (5) curricula for the post-diploma program at U2. The diploma curricula activated by the regulator and their expiry dates are highlighted below. Diploma in Public Administration, activated on 28th August 2020, expires on 28th August 2025. Diploma in Social Work and Social Administration, activated on 10th July 2024, and expires on 10th July 2029. Diploma in Information Technology, activated on 10th July 2024, and expires on 10th July 2029. Diploma in Computer Science, activated on 10th July 2024, and expires on 10th July 2029. The Diploma in Business Administration was activated on 10th July 2024 and expires on 10th July 2029. For further details about diploma curricula at U2, refer to table 5 below.

S/N	Name of the Diploma Program	Accredited Date	Expiration Date	Status
1.	Diploma in Public Administration	28/Aug/2020	28/Aug/2025	Active
2.	Diploma in Social Work and Social Administration	10/Jul/2024	10/Jul/2029	Active
3.	Diploma in Information Technology	10/Jul/2024	10/Jul/2029	Active
4.	Diploma in Computer Science	10/Jul/2024	10/Jul/2029	Active
5.	Diploma in Business Administration	10/Jul/2024	10/Jul/2029	Active

Source: The Regulator as per June and July 2025

For U3, the regulator approved three (3) diploma programs. The curricula approved by the regulator and their expiry dates are highlighted as follows. Diploma in Arabic Language, activated on 28th August 2020 and valid until 28th August 2025. The Diploma in Qur'an and Hadith, activated on 28th August 2020 and valid until 28th August 2025, and the Diploma in Education (Primary), activated on 25th April 2025 and valid until 25th April 2030.

For more details regarding diploma curricula at U3, see table 6 below.

S/N	Name Postgraduate Diploma	Accredited Date	Expiration Date	Status
1.	Diploma in Arabic Language	28/Aug/2020	28/Aug/2025	Active
2.	Diploma in Quran and Hadith	28/Aug/2020	28/Aug/2025	Active
3.	Diploma in Education – Primary	25/Apr/2025	25/Apr/2030	Active

Source: The Regulator as per June and July 2025

Undergraduate - Bachelor

The regulator approved 32 curricula for the bachelor's degree at UI. The bachelor's curricula activated by the regulator and their expiry dates are highlighted as follows. Public Health activation began on 13th December 2021 and will expire on 13th December 2026. The Medicine and Surgery curriculum was activated on 22nd August 2022 and will expire on 22nd August

2027. Environmental Health Science, activated on 20th January 2023, will expire on 20th January 2028. International Relations and Diplomacy was activated on 20th January 2023 and will expire on 20th January 2028. Administrative and Secretarial Science was activated on 17th April 2023 and will expire on 17th April 2028. Business Studies was activated on 17th April 2023 and will expire on 17th April 2028. Health Science Management, activated on 17th April 2023, will expire on 17th April 2028. Human Resource Management, activated on 17th April 2023, will expire on 17th April 2028. Procurement and Logistic Management, activated on 17th April 2023, will expire on 17th April 2028. Sharia was activated on 17th April 2023 and will expire on 17th April 2028. Tourism and Hospitality Management was activated on 17th April 2023 and will expire on 17th April 2028. Public Administration and Management, activated on 17th April 2023, will expire on 17th April 2028. Islamic Banking and Finance was activated on 13th October 2023 and will expire on 13th October 2028. Early Childhood Education, activated on 22nd January 2023, will expire on 22nd January 2029. Social Sciences and Community Development was activated on 22nd January 2023 and will expire on 22nd January 2029. Computer Science was activated on 22nd January 2023 and will expire on 22nd January 2029. Economics was activated on 22nd January 2023 and will expire on 22nd January 2029. Development Studies, activated on 22nd January 2023, will expire on 22nd January 2029. Statistics was activated on 22nd January 2023 and will expire on 22nd January 2029. Mass Communication and Environmental Science were activated on 22nd January 2023 and will expire on 22nd January 2029. Record and Library Management, activated on 22nd January 2023, will expire on 22nd January 2029. Information Technology was activated on 22nd January 2023 and will expire on 22nd January 2029. Education (Primary) was activated on 22nd January 2023 and will expire on 22nd January 2029. Education (Science) was activated on 22nd January 2023 and will expire on 22nd January 2029. Education (Horns) was activated on 22nd January 2023 and will expire on 22nd January 2029. Social Work and Social Administration was activated on 22nd January 2023 and will expire on 22nd January 2029. Islamic Studies and Arabic Language were activated on 10th July 2024 and will expire on 10th July 2029. Business Administration was activated on 10th July 2024 and will expire on 10th July 2029. Innovative Agricultural Systems was activated on 10th July 2024 and will expire on 10th July 2029. Human Resource Management was activated on 10th July 2024 and will expire on 10th July 2029. Social Work was activated on 10th July 2024 and will expire on 10th July 2029. For further details about bachelor's curricula at U1, refer to table 7 below.

Table 7 U1 Undergraduate – Bachelor’s Program

S/N	Name of the Bachelor’s Curriculum Program	Accredited date	Expiry Date	Status
1.	Science in Public Health	13/Dec/2021	13/Dec/2026	Active
2.	Medicine and Bachelor of Surgery	22/Aug/2022	22/Aug/2027	Active
3.	Environmental Health Science	20/Jan/2023	20/Jan/2028	Active
4.	International Relations and Diplomacy	20/Jan/2023	20/Jan/2028	Active
5.	Administrative and Secretarial Science	17/Apr/2023	17/Apr/2028	Active
6.	Business Studies	17/Apr/2023	17/Apr/2028	Active
7.	Health Services Management	17/Apr/2023	17/Apr/2028	Active
8.	Human Resource Management	17/Apr/2023	17/Apr/2028	Active
9.	Procurement and Logistics Management	17/Apr/2023	17/Apr/2028	Active
10.	Sharia	17/Apr/2023	17/Apr/2028	Active

11.	Tourism and Hospitality Management	17/Apr/202	17/Apr/2028	Active
12.	Public Administration and Management	17/Apr/2023	17/Apr/2028	Active
13.	Islamic Banking and Finance	13/Oct/2023	13/Oct/2028	Active
14.	Early Childhood Education	22/Jan/2024	22/Jan/2029	Active
15.	Social Sciences and Community Development	22/Jan/2024	22/Jan/2029	Active
16.	Computer Science	22/Jan/2024	22/Jan/2029	Active
17.	in Economics	22/Jan/2024	22/Jan/2029	Active
18.	Development Studies	22/Jan/2024	22/Jan/2029	Active
19.	Statistics	22/Jan/2024	22/Jan/2029	Active
20.	Mass Communication	22/Jan/2024	22/Jan/2029	Active
21.	Environmental Science	22/Jan/2024	22/Jan/2029	Active
22.	Records and Library Management	22/Jan/2024	22/Jan/2029	Active
23.	Information Technology	22/Jan/2024	22/Jan/2029	Active
24.	Education Primary (BEDP)	22/Jan/2024	22/Jan/2029	Active
25.	Science Education	22/Jan/2024	22/Jan/2029	Active
26.	Science (Horns)	22/Jan/2024	22/Jan/2029	Active
27.	Social Work and Social Administration	22/Jan/2024	22/Jan/2029	Active
28.	Islamic Studies and Arabic Language	10/Jul/2024	10/Jul/2029	Active
29.	Business Administration	10/Jul/2024	10/Jul/2029	Active
30.	Innovative Agricultural Systems	10/Jul/2024	10/Jul/2029	Active
31.	Human Resources Management	10/Jul/2024	10/Jul/2029	Active
32.	Social Work	10/Jul/2024	10/Jul/2029	Active

Source: The Regulator as per June and July 2025

The regulator approved nine (9) bachelor's degree curricula programs for U2. As highlighted below, these programs have activation and expiration dates. Conflict Resolution and Peace Building was activated on 28th August 2020 and will expire on 28th August 2025. Islamic and Arabic Studies was activated on 22nd January 2024 and will expire on 22nd January 2029. Public Administration and Management was activated on 19th April 2024 and will expire on 19th April 2029. Business Administration and Management was activated on 19th April 2024 and will expire on 19th April 2029. Education with ICT was activated on 10th July 2024 and will expire on 10th July 2029. Sharia was activated on 10th July 2024 and will expire on 10th July 2029. Procurement and Supply Chain Management was activated on 10th July 2024 and will expire on 10th July 2029. Information Technology was activated on 10th July 2024 and will expire on 10th July 2029, and Science in Computers was activated on 10th July 2024 and will expire on 10th July 2029. For more details regarding bachelor's curricula at U2, see table 8 below.

Table 8 U2 Undergraduate – Bachelors

S/N	Name	Accredited Date	Expiration Date	Status
1.	Conflict Resolution and Peace Building	28/Aug/2020	28/Aug/2025	Active
2.	Islamic and Arabic Studies	22/Jan/2024	22/Jan/2029	Active
3.	Public Administration	19/Apr/2024		Active

	and Management		19/Apr/2029	
4.	Business Administration and Management	19/Apr/2024		Active
			19/Apr/2029	
5.	Education with ICT	10/Jul/2024	10/Jul/2029	Active
6.	Sharia	10/Jul/2024	10/Jul/2029	Active
7.	Procurement and Supply Chain Management	10/Jul/2024	10/Jul/2029	Active
8.	Information Technology	10/Jul/2024	10/Jul/2029	Active
9.	Science in Computer Science	10/Jul/2024	10/Jul/2029	Active

Source: The Regulator as per June and July 2025

The regulator approved five (5) bachelor's degree curricula for U3, including curricula programs, activation dates, and expiration dates, as highlighted below. Education was activated on 19th April 2024 and will expire on 19th April 2029. Information Technology was activated on 19th April 2024 and will expire on 19th April 2029. Islamic Studies was activated on 19th April 2024 and will expire on 19th April 2029. Business Administration was activated on 19th April 2024 and will expire on 19th April 2029, and Education (Primary) was activated on 19th April 2024 and will expire on 19th April 2029. For more details on the bachelor's curricula at U3, see table 9 below.

Table 9 U3 Undergraduate – Bachelors

S/N	Name of Bachelor's Curriculum Program	Accredited Date	Expiration Date	Status
1.	Education	19/Apr/2024	19/Apr/2029	Active
2.	Information Technology	19/Apr/2024	19/Apr/2029	Active
3.	Islamic Studies	19/Apr/2024	19/Apr/2029	Active
4.	Business Administration	19/Apr/2024	19/Apr/2029	Active
5.	Education – Primary	25/Apr/2025	25/Apr/2030	Active

Source: The Regulator as per June and July 2025

Undergraduate - Diploma

The regulator approved thirteen (13) curricula for the Diploma program at UI. The curricula activated by the regulator, together with their expiry dates, are highlighted below. The Diploma in Education (Primary) was activated on 20th January 2023 and expires on 20th January 2028. The Advanced Diploma in Health Services Management was activated on 17th April 2023 and will expire on 17th April 2028. The Diploma in Public Administration was activated on 17th April 2023 and will expire on 17th April 2028. The Diploma in Business Administration was activated on 17th April 2023 and will expire on 17th April 2028. The Diploma in Business Administration and Management was activated on 17th April 2023 and will expire on 17th April 2028. The Diploma in Arabic Language was activated on 22nd January 2023 and will expire on

22nd January 2029. The Diploma in Food Science and Technology was activated on 22nd January 2023 and will expire on 22nd January 2029. The Diploma in Computer Science and Information Technology was activated on 22nd January 2023 and will expire on 22nd January 2029. The Diploma in Records Management was activated on 22nd January 2023 and will expire on 22nd January 2029. The Diploma in Library and Information was activated on 22nd January 2023 and will expire on 22nd January 2029. The Diploma in Law was activated on 22nd January 2023 and will expire on 22nd January 2029. The Diploma in Early Childhood Education was activated on 22nd January 2023 and will expire on 22nd January 2029. The Diploma in Social Work and Community Development was activated on 22nd January 2023 and will expire on 22nd January 2029. The Diploma in Business Studies is currently under review, was activated on 17th May 2017, and will expire on 17th May 2029. For more detail regarding diploma `curricula at U1, see table 10 below.

Table 10 U1 Undergraduate – Diploma

S/N	Name of Curriculum Diploma	Accredited Date	Expiration Date	Status
1.	Diploma in Education – Primary	20/Jan/2023	20/Jan/2028	Active
2.	Advanced Diploma in Health Services Management	17/Apr/2023	17/Apr/2028	Active
3.	Diploma in Public Administration	17/Apr/2023	17/Apr/2028	Active
4.	Diploma in Business Administration	17/Apr/2023	17/Apr/2028	Active
5.	Diploma in Arabic Language	22/Jan/2024	22/Jan/2029	Active
6.	Diploma in Food Science and Technology	22/Jan/2024	22/Jan/2029	Active
7.	Diploma in Computer Science and Information Technology	22/Jan/2024	22/Jan/2029	Active
8.	Diploma in Records Management	22/Jan/2024	22/Jan/2029	Active
9.	Diploma in Library and Information Science	22/Jan/2024	22/Jan/2029	Active
10.	Diploma in Law	22/Jan/2024	22/Jan/2029	Active
11.	Diploma in Early Childhood Education	22/Jan/2024	22/Jan/2029	Active
12.	Diploma in Social Work and Community Development	30/Jan/2025	30/Jan/2030	Active
13.	Diploma in Business Studies	22/May/2017	22/May/2022	Under Review

Source: The Regulator as per June and July 2025

Undergraduate-Certificate

The regulator approved one (1) certificate curriculum for UI. A Certificate Curriculum was activated along with its expiry date by the regulator, as highlighted below. The Higher Education Access Certificate in Humanities was activated on 10th July 2024 and will expire on 10th July 2029. For further information about the curriculum of the certificate at U1, see Table 11 below.

Table 11 U1 Undergraduate – Certificate

S/N	Name	Accredited Date	Expiration Date	Status
1.	Higher Education Access Certificate – Humanities	10/Jul/2024	10/Jul/2029	Active

Source: The Regulator as per June and July 2025

However, by the time this research was carried out in June and July 2025, no certificate courses appeared on the regulator's online database for either U1 or U2.

Data from the Islamic Institutions of Higher Education

This section presents the results of the curricula actively implemented at various Islamic institutions of higher education, aiming to establish a correlation with the regulator's results mentioned above. However, due to limited space and to avoid repetition, this section focuses on the correlation of results from either of the two study subjects. (Islamic University In Uganda, 2025) and (Al-Mustafa Islamic College, 2025).

UI Results

This section shows curricula results for undergraduate and postgraduate students from Subject U1 below.

Undergraduate–Certificate

U1 offers a total of 17 certificate-level curricula, and they are highlighted as follows: Administrative Law, Arabic Language I, Arabic Language II, Arabic Language III, Early Childhood Education, English Language Proficiency (Advanced Level), English Language Proficiency (Beginner's Level), English Language Proficiency (Intermediate Level), General Nursing, Imamship, Library and Information Science, Midwifery, Public Administration, Records Management, and Higher Education Certificates in Biological Science, Humanities, and Physical Science. One of U1's sixteen curricula aligns with the regulator's list; for further details, see table 2.1 and refer to table 11 in the previous section.

Table 2.1 U1 Undergraduate – certificate

S/N	Name of the Certificate Program	Years
1.	Administrative Law	1
2.	Arabic Language	1
3.	Arabic Language Level II	1
4.	Arabic Language Level III	1
5.	Early Childhood Education	1
6.	English Language Proficiency (Advanced Level)	1
7.	English Language Proficiency (Beginners Level)	1

English Language Proficiency (Intermediate Level)	1
Nursing General Nursing	3
Imamship	1
Library and Information	2
Midwifery	3
Public Administration	1
Records Management	2
Higher Education Certificate (Biological Sciences)	1
Higher Education Certificate (Physical Science)	1

Source: The U1 as per June and July 2025

Undergraduate - Diploma

U1 offers a total of fourteen (14) diploma-level curricula, and they are highlighted as follows: Health Services Management, Arabic Diploma Programme, Business Studies, Computer Science and Information Technology, Food Science and Technology, General Nursing, General Nursing (Extension), Guidance and Counselling, Library and Information Science, Midwifery (Extension), Primary Education (External), Public Administration and Management, Records Management, and Social Work and Community Development. Seven (7) diploma curricula of U1 are missing; refer to table 10 for more details about the seven, as seen in table 2.2 above.

Table 2 1 U1 Undergraduate – Diploma

S/N	Name of the Diploma curriculum	Years
1.	Advanced Diploma In Health Services Management	1
2.	Arabic Diploma Programme	2
3.	Diploma in General Nursing	3
4.	Diploma in General Nursing (Extension)	1.5
5.	Diploma in Guidance and Counselling	2
6.	Diploma in Midwifery (Extension)	1.5
7.	Diploma In Primary Education (External)	2

Source: The U1 as per the June and July 2025

Undergraduate – Bachelors

There is no association between the eight bachelor’s curricula of U1 (see table 2.3); for the purpose of correlation, see Table 7 in the previous section.

Table 2. 3 U1 Undergraduates – Bachelors

S/N	Name of the Bachelor’s Program	Years
1.	Bachelor of Arts Education	3
2.	Bachelor of Biomedical Sciences	4
3.	Bachelor of Business Computing	3
4.	Bachelor Of Cultural Heritage Studies	3

5.	Bachelor of Dawah & Sociology	3
6.	Bachelor of Laws	4
7.	Bachelor of Science in Food Science and Nutrition	4
8.	Bachelor of Science in Political Science	3

Source: The U1 as per the June and July 2025

Postgraduate—Master's Curriculum

U1 provides a total of nineteen (19) Doctor of Philosophy programs, as highlighted below: Applied Linguistics, Arabic Language, International Relations and Diplomacy, Kiswahili, Sharia, Business Administration, Education, Information Technology Management, Islamic Banking and Finance, Laws, Public Administration and Management, Public Health, Science in Communication and Media Studies, Environmental Science, Zoology, Peace and Conflict Resolution, Islamic Studies (English), and Political Science. Two (2) master's curricula of U1, two programs are less unrelated. See Table 3 of the regulator's list and table 2.4.

Table 2. 4 Postgraduate – Masters

S/N	Name of Master's Program	YEAR
1.	Applied Linguistics	2
2.	Zoology	2
3.	Science in Political Science	2

Source: The U1 as per June and July 2025

Postgraduate—Postgraduate Diploma

U1 offers a total of ten (10) postgraduate diploma programs and curricula highlighted as follows: Computer Science and Information Technology, Education, Educational Management and Administration, International Relations and Diplomacy, Islamic Banking and Finance, Project Planning and Management, International Affairs and Humanitarian Diplomacy, Management and Teaching at Higher Education, and Public Administration and Management. There is one uncorrelated postgraduate diploma program at U1. See table 4 of the regulator's list and table 2.5 below.

Table 2. 5 Postgraduate Diploma

S/N	Name of the Postgraduate Diploma	Year
1.	Computer Science and Information Technology	1

Source: The U1 as per June and July 2025

Postgraduate—Doctor of Philosophy

U1 offers a total of seven (7) Doctor of Philosophy-level curricula, and they are highlighted as follows: Arabic Language, Business Administration, Education, Islamic Banking and Finance, Islamic Studies, Sharia, and Law. Out of the seven postgraduate Doctor of Philosophy programs at U1 for the purpose of correlation, see table 2.6 below, and also refer to the table of the regulator's results.

S/N	Doctor of Philosophy	Year
1.	Arabic Language	3
2.	Business Administration	3
3.	Education	3
4.	Islamic Banking and Finance	2
5.	Islamic Studies	3
6.	Sharia	3
7.	Law	3

Source: The U1 as per June and July 2025

U2 Results

This section presents undergraduate certificates, diplomas, and bachelor's degrees.

Undergraduate – Certificate

U2 offers one curriculum program on the Leadership and Management Skills certificate refer to table 3.1.

S/N	Certificate Program
1.	Leadership and management skills.

Source: U2 5th Graduation List

Undergraduate – Diploma

U2 offers three diploma curriculum programs: Early Childhood Education, Information Technology, and Computer Science.

Table 3. 2 U2 Undergraduate Diploma Curriculum

S/N	Certificate
1.	Early Childhood Education
2.	Information Technology
3.	Computer Science

Source: U2 5th Graduation List

Undergraduate - Bachelors

For U2, two (2) curricula do not correlate; see table 3.3 below.

Table 3. 3 U2 Undergraduate – Bachelor’s Curricula

S/N	Bachelors
1.	Human Resource Management
2.	Islamic Banking and Finance

Source: U2 5th Graduation List

U3 Results

Undergraduate - Certificate

U3 provides a diverse selection of 6 certificate programs: National Certificate in Business Administration, Accounting and Finance, Information and Communication Technology, Fashion and Garment Design, Electricity Installation Systems and Maintenance, and Automotive Mechanics. See table 4.1 below.

Tabel 4. 1 U3 Undergraduate - Certificate -

S/N	National Certificate
1.	Business Administration
2.	Accounting and Finance
3.	Information and Communication Technology
4.	Fashion and Garment Design
5.	Electrical Installation Systems and Maintenance
6.	Automotive Mechanics

Source: U3 as per June and July 2025

Undergraduate-Diploma

University 3 provides 11 diploma programs: Business Administration, Accounting and Finance, Public Administration, Information Technology, Guidance and Counselling, Islamic Studies, Arabic Language, National Diploma in Hotel Management and Institutional Catering, National Diploma in Fashion and Garment, National Diploma in Electrical Engineering, and National Diploma in Mechanical Engineering. See table 4.2 below.

Table 4. 2 Undergraduate Diploma Curricula

S/N	Diploma
1.	Business Administration
2.	Accounting and Finance
3.	Public Administration
4.	Information Technology
5.	Guidance and Counselling
6.	Islamic Studies
7.	Arabic Language
8.	National Diploma in Hotel Management and Institutional Catering
9.	National Diploma in Fashion and Garment
10.	National Diploma in Electro Engineering
11.	National Diploma in Mechanical Engineering

Source: U3 as per the June and July 2025

Undergraduate–Bachelors

U3, Bachelor's Curriculum, is inconsistent with one of the regulators. See table

Table 4. 3 U3 Undergraduate - Bachelor's Curricular

S/N	Bachelors
1.	Science with Education

Source: U3 as per the June and July 2025

Discussions

This section offers a descriptive analysis of the findings based on three key dimensions: (1) the role of the regulatory authority (UNCHE), (2) curriculum status across Islamic Institutions of Higher Learning (U1, U2, U3), and (3) an EIM-IW synthesis (Education, Institutional Mandate, Islamization of Knowledge and Worldview), which will be elaborated on in the concluding segment.

The Regulator

First, the regulator granted U1, U2, and U3 institutions private accreditation status. Secondly, the regulator granted Type: Registered Status to U1, issued a provisional license as another degree-awarding institution, and awarded a provisional license to operate as a university. Thirdly, regarding accreditation to run a campus within a district. U1 was licensed to operate four campuses in Mbale, Arua, and two in Kampala. U2 was licensed to operate a single campus in Kampala, as was U3. For the Doctor of Philosophy program, the regulator awarded U1 to oversee nine PhD programs, each lasting several years. The first cohort began on 27th August 2018, focusing on the history and education curricula. The second cohort comprised three

programs centered on Sharia, Arabic, and Islamic Studies; operations started on 30th November 2018. The third cohort included only the Islamic Banking and Finance program, focusing on the Islamic Banking and Finance Curriculum license, which commenced on 14th March 2021. The fourth cohort had two programs licensed to operate on 22nd January 2024, specializing in business administration and Kiswahili. The fifth cohort focused on the law curriculum, as this program was the last to be licensed to operate on 28th April 2025.

However, the five batched curriculum licenses expire from earliest to latest. The first batch, consisting of two programs, expires on 27th April 2028. The second batch, with three programs, expires on 30th November 2028. Additionally, one program in batch three expires on 1st March 2031. The following two programs in batch four expire on 22nd March 2031. Finally, batch five expires on 28th April 2035.

The first batch to expire is History and Education, followed by the second batch of Sharia, Arabic, and Islamic Studies. Regarding the diploma of the curriculum to expire, it comprises Islamic Banking and Finance. Following that, the fourth batch of curriculum to expire is business administration. The fifth batch of curriculum for the U1 Master's includes Kiswahili. Finally, as previously elaborated, the law is also set to expire.

For U2 and U3, the Doctor of Philosophy curriculum and program are unavailable on both the institutions and the regulator's databases. Regarding the master's curriculum for U1, the regulator approved the teaching of 19 programs, each lasting five years. The curriculum is divided into eight batches. The first batch started on 1st March 2021, focusing on education and specializing in educational psychology. The second batch began on 13th December 2021, with a curriculum centered on law. The third batch, launched on 20th January 2023, included International Relations and History. The fourth batch, Business Administration and Public Administration and Management, became operational on 17th April 2023. The fifth batch of master's programs, accredited by the regulator, includes Religion, Peace and Conflict Resolution, Sharia, and Arabic Language, beginning on 21st August 2023. Batch six, accredited on 13th October 2023, covers Islamic banking and finance. Batch seven, accredited on 22nd January 2024, includes six programs: Communication and Media, Islamic Studies (English), Kiswahili, Environmental Science, Botany and Zoology, and Islamic Studies (Arabic version). Finally, the eighth and last master's curriculum to be accredited by the regulator started on 30th January 2025 and includes economics and social work.

However, the eight-batch curriculum activated in descending order expires as follows: the first batch on 1 March 2026, the second batch on 13th December 2026, the third batch on 20th January 2025, the fourth batch on 17th April 2028, the fifth batch on 21st August 2028, the sixth on 13th October 2028, the seventh on 22nd January 2029, and the eighth and final batch on 30th January 2030.

Regarding U2 and U3 accreditation of the curriculum, the study indicates that the regulator has not accredited the two institutions to offer the master's program. Regarding the bachelor's curriculum for U1, the regulator granted a five-year license for each of the 32 bachelor's programs to U1. This study divided the programs into seven batches. Batch one was activated on 13th December 2021, focusing on public health curricula and programs. Batch two was activated on 22th August 2022, comprising one program in medicine and surgery. Batch three became active on 20th January 2023, including two programs in Environmental Health Science and International Relations and Diplomacy. Batch four, consisting of seven curricula,

was activated on 17th April 2023, covering Administrative and Secretarial Science, Business Studies, Health Science Management, Human Resource Management, Procurement and Logistics Management, Sharia, and Tourism and Hospitality Management. Batch five, activated on 13th October 2023, included two programs in public administration and management and Islamic banking and finance. Batch six was activated on 22nd January 2024 and consists of fourteen programs: Early Childhood Education, Social Sciences and Community Development, Computer Science, Economics, Development Studies, Statistics, Mass Communication, Environmental Science, Record and Library Management, Information Technology, Education (Primary), Education (Science), Education (Honors), and Social Work and Social Administration. Batch seven became active on 10th July 2024, comprising six programs for Islamic Studies and Arabic Language, Business Administration, Innovative Agricultural Systems, Human Resource Management, and Social Work.

However, U1's seven batches of bachelor curriculum activated by the regulator will expire in descending order: the first batch on 13th December 2026, followed by the second batch on 22nd August 2027, the third batch on 20th January 2028, the fourth batch on 17th April 2028, the fifth batch on 13th October 2028, the sixth batch on 22nd January 2029, and finally the seventh batch on 10th July 2029.

Regarding the bachelor's curriculum for U2, the regulator granted a five-year license for each curriculum. This study categorizes the curricula into four batches. Batch one includes the Conflict Resolution and Peace Building curriculum, which was activated on 28th August 2020. Batch two covers Islamic and Arabic studies, activated by the regulator on 22nd January 2024. Batch three features two curricula in public administration and management and business administration and management, both activated on 19th April 2024. Batch four comprises five curricula activated on 10th July 2024: Education with ICT, Sharia, Procurement and Supply Chain Management, Information Technology, and Computer Science.

However, the regulator has scheduled the curriculum for the U2 Bachelor's batches to expire. Batch one will expire on 28th August 2025, batch two on 22nd January 2029, batch three on 19th April 2029, and batch four on 10th July 2029.

Regarding the bachelor's curriculum for U3, the regulator granted a five-year license for each of the five curricula. This study groups the curriculum into a single batch. This sole batch, which was launched on 19th April 2024, comprises Education, Information Technology, Islamic Studies, Business Administration, and Education (Primary) programs. However, the regulator scheduled the U3 Bachelor's batch curriculum to expire on 19th April 2029.

Regarding the diploma curriculum for U1, the regulator issued a five-year license for each of the 13 curricula. This study categorizes curricula into five batches; the first batch was activated on 20th January 2023 by the regulator with a single program in Education (Primary). The second batch includes four curricula, activated on 17th April 2023, comprising the Advanced Diploma in Health Services Management, valid until 17th April 2028; the Diploma in Public Administration; the Diploma in Business Administration; and the Diploma in Business Administration and Management. Batch three was activated on 22nd January 2024, focusing on a single curriculum in the Arabic language. Batch four consists of six curricula: Food Science and Technology, activated on 22nd January 2024; Computer Science and Information Technology; Records Management; Library and Information; Law; Early

Childhood Education; and Social Work and Community Development. The regulator activated Batch five on 17th May 2017 with one curriculum.

However, the U1 diploma batch of curricula is scheduled to expire as follows: batch one in 2028, batch two on 17th April 2028, batch three on 22nd January 2029, batch four on 22nd January 2029, and batch five, which expired on 17th May 2022, is under review by the regulator. Regarding the Postgraduate Diploma program for U1, the regulator granted a five-year license for each of the 10 curricula. This study divided the postgraduate curricula into six batches; Batch one was activated on 17th April 2023, comprising Project Planning and Management and Human Resources Management. The regulator activated Batch two on 21st August 2023 and included only one program in Management and Teaching Higher Education. Batch three features the Islamic Banking and Finance curriculum, activated on 13th October 2023. Batch four's curriculum was activated on 22nd January 2024, focusing on educational management and administration. Batch five includes a single Education, International Affairs, and Humanitarian Diplomacy program, activated on 10th July 2024. The regulator activated Batch six on 30th January 2025, containing two curricula: Child Protection and International Relations and Diplomacy. The regulator schedules the U1 Postgraduate Diploma curricula to expire as follows: batch one on 17th April 2028, batch two on 21st August 2028, batch three on 13th October 2028, batch four on 22nd January 2029, batch five on 10th July 2029, and batch six on 30th January 2030.

Regarding the diploma curriculum for U2, the regulator granted a five-year license for each of the five curricula. This study classified the postgraduate curricula into two batches. Batch one was activated by the regulator on 28th August 2020 and includes one curriculum in public administration. Batch two comprises four curricula activated on 10th July 2024: Social Work and Social Administration, Information Technology, Computer Science, and Business Administration.

However, the regulator has scheduled the U2 Diploma curricula to expire; batch one expires on 28th August 2025, while batch two expires on 10th July 2029. Regarding the diploma curriculum for U3, the regulator awarded a five-year license for each of the three curricula. This study categorized the diploma curricula into three batches. Batch one, which includes Arabic Language, Qur'an, and Hadith, was regulated and activated on 28th August 2020. Batch two, which covers education (primary), was activated on 25th April 2025. The regulator has scheduled the expiry of these curricula: batch one will expire on 28th August 2025, and batch two on 25 April 2030.

Regarding the certificate curriculum for U1, the regulator granted a five-year license for each of the three curricula. This study classified the certificate curriculum by batch. The regulator activated Batch one on 10th July 2024, and the curriculum program is the Higher Education Access Certificate in Humanities. However, the U1 certificate batch one curriculum is set to expire on 10th July 2029.

For U2 and U3, the regulator's online database regarding accredited certificate curricula and their programs is empty. The descriptive analysis emphasizes U1's institutional dominance in curriculum development and accreditation across all tiers of higher education—PhD, Master's, Bachelor's, Diploma, Postgraduate Diploma, and Certificate. This extensive institutional mandate showcases U1's well-established and expanding academic infrastructure. In contrast, U2 shows a more limited program scope, especially at the postgraduate level, while

U3 is still in the initial stages of curriculum accreditation. Furthermore, the timing pattern of program activation shows a clear acceleration in curriculum development after 2020, particularly for U1. This trend may suggest a broader shift in institutional readiness, regulatory support, or policy changes in higher Islamic education.

However, inconsistencies in curriculum renewal cycles and the lack of public data for several program levels at U2 and U3 reveal gaps in regulatory transparency and institutional reporting. These shortcomings highlight the need for greater accountability, better institutional communication with regulatory authorities, and more effective monitoring and evaluation mechanisms.

Islamic Institutions of Higher Learning

This section focuses on items that are not in the regulatory database but are present at the university. It also considers items that have been approved by the regulator but are missing from the university database. Out of nine (9) active Doctor of Philosophy curricula, U1 operates only seven. The databases for UI Curricula 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 8, and 9 are active, while items 1 and 8 are not listed among the PhD programs at this institution. See the Doctor of Philosophy curriculum table on page for more details.

According to its database, out of ten (19) master curricula activated by the regulatory institution, U1 runs nineteen. Curricula 1 and 19 are somewhat different from the ones in the regulator's list. The curriculum name for item 16 in the U1 database is incomplete; for more details on the two scenarios, refer to the Master's Curriculum table. Out of ten (10) postgraduate curricula activated by the regulator, Institution U1 reports running 10 curricula according to its database. The postgraduate diploma accredited Curriculum 9 is not listed in U1's database, but another program is called the postgraduate in Computer Science and Information Technology. For more details, refer to the Table UI Postgraduate Diploma.

Out of thirty-two (32) bachelor curricula activated for Institution U1 to operate by the regulator, the available online database shows that UI offers a total of 35 programs, three more than listed by the regulator. Of the 32 curricula on the regulator's list, U1 runs 31; however, curriculum 11 is unavailable on the UI online database. The regulator's curriculum 11 is not reflected in U1's database. Conversely, curricula 8, 9, 11, 12, 14, 20, and 32 are not on the regulator's list. For further details, refer to the U1 bachelor's Programmes Table.

Out of thirty-two (13) diploma curricula activated for Institution U1 to be run by the regulator. According to the available online database, UI runs a total of 14 programs, one more than the list of the regulator. Refer to the U1 diploma and regulator's diploma tables for more details.

According to the available online database, out of one (1) certificate curriculum activated by the regulator for Institution U1 to operate, UI offers 17 programs, one more than the list provided by the regulator. For more details, refer to the U1 Certificate and regulator tables. Out of nine (9) bachelor's curricula activated by the regulator for Institution U2 to run, the available online database shows that U2 operates a total of 12 programs, which is three more than the list provided by the regulator. For further details, refer to the U1 Certificate and regulator tables. For additional information, consult the U2 and regulator tables section.

Of the nine (9) bachelor's curricula activated by the regulator for Institution U2 to operate, U2

offers a total of 12 programs according to the available online database, three more than the regulator listed. For more details, refer to the U1 Certificate and regulator tables. Additional information can be found in the U2 and regulator tables section.

The available online database shows that U2 offers 12 programs out of nine (9) bachelor's curricula activated by the regulator for Institution U2 to operate. Three more than the regulator listed. For more details, refer to the U1 Certificate and regulator tables. For additional information, see the sections on U2 and the regulator tables.

Out of nine (9) bachelor's curricula approved by the regulator for Institution U2 to operate, U2 offers a total of 12 programs according to the 5th Graduation list, which is three more than the regulator listed. For more details, refer to the U1 Certificate and regulator tables. For additional information, see the U2 and regulator tables section. Out of five (5) bachelor's programs authorized by the regulator for Institution U3 to operate, U5 runs a total of 5 programs, as listed by the regulator. For more details, see U3 and the regulator's curriculum tables. The available online database shows that U3 offers 11 programs out of the three (3) diploma curricula activated by the regulator for Institution U3 to operate. Nine additional ones are not listed by the regulator. For more details, refer to the diploma's U3 and regulator curriculum tables. Institution U3 operates six (6) certificate curricula; the regulator database does not contain information about activating the certificate curriculum for U3. Refer to the diploma's U3 and regulator curriculum tables for more details.

EIM-IW Synthesis

The set of universal principles governing the process of epistemology integration values are Tawhid (monotheism), purification (Tazkiyyah), and the value of umrān civilization, societal development, and prosperity. (Fathi Hassan Malkawi, 2019, p. 217)

The Islamization and Integration of Islamic Universities in Uganda. First, the results indicate that Islamic institutions have approximately 137 curricula covering undergraduate and postgraduate programs. This does not include synthesized curricula that recurred across institutions and programs between June and July 2025, when this survey was conducted, reducing the number to 53.

Synthesized curricula

Muqarrar 30, four of which are maṣḍar, are based on the Written Revelation: Islamic Studies, Islamic Banking and Finance, Qur'an and Hadith, Da'wah, and Sociology. The remaining *Muqarrar* are not of wahyu maṣḍar. For the Created World maṣḍar, the societal aspect is emphasized. Regarding the Tool of Reason, the means are Written Revelation (n=2), Created World (n=25), and both Written Revelation and Created World (n=3). As for maṣḍar and the Tool of Reason, (n=2) are positive while (n=28) are negative. Therefore, there is very limited integration of knowledge (two) and Islamization of knowledge (three).

Psychological *Muqarrar* consisted of six (6) curricular components; no maṣḍar was found in the Written Revelation (n=0). For the created world, maṣḍar was present in all six cases (n=6). The tools of reason considered were written revelation (n=0) and the created world (n=6). Regarding maṣḍar and the Tool of Reason, the results were negative (n=6) and positive (n=0). Consequently, there was neither integration of knowledge nor Islamization of knowledge within the *Muqarrar*.

The *Muqarrar* of Law had three curricula: maşdar on Written Revelation (n=1) and maşdar on the Created World (n=2). The tools of reason included written revelation (n=1) and the created world (n=2). The maşdar and Tool of Reason were absent in negative (n=0) and positive (n=0) forms. Therefore, there was neither integration of knowledge nor Islamization of expertise within the *Muqarrar*.

Muqarrar of Physical had fourteen (14) curricula; maşdar on Written Revelation (n=0). For the Created World, maşdar (n=14). The tool of reason, the means, was written revelation (n=0) and the created world (n=14). Regarding maşdar and Tool of Reason, negative (n=14), while positive (n=0). Thus, there was neither integration of knowledge nor Islamization of expertise in the *Muqarrar*.

Conclusion

This study confirms that the regulator and Islamic institutions are vital in guiding the quality and direction of Islamic higher education in Uganda. To remain relevant in the Fourth Industrial Revolution (4IR) era, they must adopt a balanced approach to curriculum reform. This involves integrating the three core sources of Islamic knowledge: the Written Revelation (waḥyu), the Created World (empirical reality), and the Tools of Reason ('aql). Although this study focused on Islamic institutions, it is important to recognize that many public and private universities also contribute to the broader higher education landscape. Future research could expand the analysis to include these institutions for a more comprehensive understanding of curriculum development trends in Uganda.

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